

CARBON REMOVAL CERTIFICATION FRAMEWORK IMPLICATIONS ON STEEL INDUSTRY

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Executive Summary:

A voluntary approach to certify carbon reductions made in Europe has been proposed by the European Union (EU) and is called the Carbon Removal Certification Framework. The framework delineates criteria for superior carbon reductions and delineates protocols for monitoring, documenting, and verifying their validity. It seeks to expose greenwashing, increase the scope of carbon removal initiatives, and show how committed companies are to environmental responsibility. With a focus on the steel industry, which contributes significantly to carbon emissions, the EU's Carbon Removal Certification Framework aims to mitigate climate change by certifying carbon removals. The framework seeks to ensure a favorable climate effect by making it easier to implement high-quality carbon removal initiatives. In order to support the EU's goal of becoming carbon neutral by 2050, it promotes the steel industry's adoption of sustainable practices. The plan addresses issues like greenwashing and ensures the credibility of carbon reduction activities by outlining procedures for tracking, reporting, and validating carbon removals. The study recognizes the negative effects that steel production has on the environment, particularly when it comes to the blast furnace process, which is directly linked to significant carbon emissions.

The purpose of this research is to examine the various aspects that the EU's Carbon Removal Certification Framework has for the EU steel sector. We hope to shed light on this framework's role in guiding the steel industry toward sustainability and a low-carbon future by investigating its possible effects. This thorough analysis includes a methodology, consequences, and strategic suggestions in addition to a review of the literature. It gives stakeholders practical advice on how to negotiate the changing environmental certification and responsibility landscape.

2 Introduction

The Carbon Removal Certification Framework is a voluntary EU-wide framework that aims to certify carbon removals generated in Europe. It lays out standards for what constitutes high-quality carbon removals as well as the procedures for tracking, reporting, and confirming the legitimacy of these removals. The framework is designed to scale up carbon removal activities and fight greenwashing by empowering businesses to show their action in this field.

The framework will facilitate and speed up the deployment of high-quality carbon removal activities in the EU, resulting in an unambiguous positive climate impact, while fighting greenwashing. Regulations for carbon removals' monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) are outlined in the proposal. The main goal of the European Union's (EU) planned Carbon Removal Certificate Framework is to combat climate change by certifying carbon removals produced in Europe. While the direct impact on industries can vary, including the steel industry.

It might help the EU countries which have increased carbon emission till 2022. According to data, most of the EU's total CO₂ emissions coming from Germany alone. France, Italy, and Poland ranked second and third, respectively, among EU countries that released the most CO₂ in 2022. (*CO₂ Emissions from EU Territorial Energy Use: -2.8% - Products Eurostat News - Eurostat, n.d.*)

The foundation of contemporary civilization is steel. Buildings, infrastructure, shipping, packaging, and transportation all use it. Germany and other industrialized nations appear to utilize a lot of steel per person. The need for steel will only increase in developing nations as living standards rise. Up to 2050, steel will be in strong demand (Bhaskar et al., 2020)

The predominant method in steel production, the blast furnace process, is intrinsically linked to substantial carbon emissions. This fundamental technique involves the reduction of iron ore into molten iron using coke, derived from coal. Iron ore is reduced to molten iron when a burst of hot air combines with the coke in the furnace, creating carbon monoxide (CO). Simultaneously, impurities form slag. Despite its efficiency in yielding pig iron, a key input for steel, the blast furnace process is a major source of environmental carbon emissions. The combustion of coke releases carbon dioxide (CO₂), contributing to greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, the combustion generates carbon monoxide, pivotal in the reduction of iron ore. Recognizing the high carbon intensity, the blast furnace process underscores the steel industry's challenge in reducing its environmental impact and transitioning to more sustainable production methods.

3 Literature Review

What is Carbon Removal Certification Framework

The European Union (EU) is steadfast in its commitment to achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, prompting the establishment of a comprehensive carbon removal certification framework. This voluntary mechanism, designed to counter greenwashing, aims to verify businesses' genuine efforts in reducing greenhouse gas emissions through technological and natural means within Europe (Carbon Removal Certification, n.d.). The intricacies of crafting such a framework are illuminated in studies by (Oldenburg et al., 2009 ; Arcusa & Sprenkle-Hyppolite, 2022). Oldenburg et al. (2009) proposed a certification process for geologic carbon sequestration, evaluating safety and efficacy at locations in Texas and California, revealing challenges in ensuring carbon removal operations' effectiveness. Arcusa & Sprenkle-Hyppolite (2022) emphasized the need for transparent and impartial oversight in certifying carbon dioxide removal standards, addressing current shortcomings. Margaras et al. (2022) explored governmental responses to the EU's certification initiative, highlighting the importance of openness and quality control in aligning certifications with carbon reduction goals and sustainable practices. These studies collectively underscore the complexities and vital considerations in establishing a credible framework for certifying carbon removal efforts in the pursuit of EU's ambitious carbon neutrality targets.

Carbon emission by steel industry in EU

According to Pardo & Moya (2013), the EU's steel sector significantly contributes to carbon emissions. On the other hand, new technologies like Top Gas Recycling have the potential to improve things (Pardo & Moya, 2013). It has been noted that technology and its spread can help reduce energy consumption and CO₂ emissions at the plant level (Pardo et al., 2012). Holappa (2020) highlights that the industry bears a considerable percentage of the anthropogenic CO₂ emissions and calls for significant reductions. It has been emphasized that modernization and the adoption of new techniques have the ability to reduce some CO₂ emissions (Holappa, 2020). It has been suggested to categorize CO₂ emissions in the steel sector and calculate total emissions for various process combinations (Lisienko et al., 2015).

Carbon Reduction in Steel Industry

Reducing greenhouse gas emissions is an issue for the EU steel sector, and several initiatives have been put forth to this end. According to Axelson et al. (2021), material efficiency is a crucial decarbonization tactic that can necessitate significant adjustments to company strategies. Another approach that is thought to be feasible is CO₂ removal, specifically by a shift reaction and physical absorption; the projected costs of this method are similar to those of CO₂ removal in coal-fired power plants (Gielen, 2003). Through the Clean Steel Partnership, which emphasizes carbon direct avoidance, smart carbon utilization, and circular economy techniques, the sector is dedicated to lowering its CO₂ emissions (Rieger et al., 2021).

4 Methodology

Research Approach

Utilizing secondary data sources and a qualitative research methodology, this study explores the effects of the Carbon Removal Certification Framework on the European Union's steel industry. The analysis of secondary data, which includes reports, official documents, and current literature, will yield insights into the effects of the certification framework on the steel industry.

Data Collection

The primary source of data is scholarly articles, government publications, industry reports, and documentation related to the Carbon Removal Certification Framework proposed by the European Union. The selected sources will cover a range of perspectives, including regulatory documents, industry responses, and academic analyses. Data will be collected from reputable databases, official websites, and scholarly repositories to ensure reliability and comprehensiveness.

Reliability

To ensure the reliability of the data, only information from reputable sources and scholarly publications will be considered. Official documents from EU institutions, reports from recognized industry associations, and peer-reviewed articles will form the basis of the analysis. The use of established literature contributes to the credibility and accuracy of the findings.

Validity

The validity of the study is ensured by focusing on reliable and up-to-date sources. By incorporating recent publications and official documents related to the Carbon Removal Certification Framework, the study aims to provide accurate and relevant insights into the implications on the steel industry. Attention will be given to the credibility of sources and the alignment of findings with the objectives of the study.

Ethical Considerations

Because secondary data used in this study is publicly available, privacy and confidentiality problems are eliminated. To uphold ethical norms and academic integrity, the original sources shall be properly credited.

5 Implications

Business Implications:

- **Emission Reduction Pressures:** The steel industry is a significant emitter of carbon dioxide due to the nature of its production processes. The Carbon Removal Certificate Framework may exert additional pressure on the industry to reduce emissions further. This could lead to the exploration of cleaner technologies and processes within the steel manufacturing sector.
- **Regulatory Compliance and Legal Obligations:** Depending on the finalization and adoption of the framework, steel producers in the EU may need to navigate new regulatory requirements. Compliance with certification rules and quality criteria could become a legal obligation for the industry.
- **Market Competitiveness:** The carbon removal certification framework significantly enhances market competitiveness in the EU steel industry by providing a competitive edge to producers engaged in carbon removal. Certified businesses appeal to environmentally conscious consumers, potentially influencing market share. Emphasizing sustainability, the framework aligns with growing eco-friendly preferences, enabling certified steel products to stand out and attract consumers prioritizing sustainability.
- **Supply Chain and Certification Requirements:** The steel industry's supply chain may be affected as the framework introduces new certification requirements. Steel producers might need to evaluate and optimize their supply chains to meet the sustainability criteria outlined in the certification framework.
- **Financial Implications:** The certification process and compliance with the framework may entail additional costs for the steel industry. However, certified carbon removals may also open avenues for access to green financing, providing financial support for the implementation of cleaner technologies.
- **Resource and Energy Intensity Considerations:** Resource and energy intensity considerations in the carbon removal certification framework prompt the EU steel industry to reassess practices, optimizing solutions for environmental sustainability. Aligning with certification criteria, this encourages innovation in minimizing resource use and energy intensity, promoting more efficient and eco-friendly production methods.

Ethical Implication:

- **Unequal Industry Impact:** The framework's impact on the steel industry may not be uniform across all players. Larger, more financially robust companies might find it easier to adapt to sustainable practices, while smaller or less economically stable enterprises may struggle to comply. This inequality could exacerbate existing disparities within the industry.
- **Technology Accessibility and Innovation Challenges:** Smaller or less technologically advanced steel producers may face challenges in adopting new, sustainable technologies required for certification. The framework could inadvertently stifle innovation and lead to a technological divide within the industry, raising ethical concerns about equitable access to environmentally friendly practices.

- **Market Imbalances:** The certification framework may create a scenario where EU steel producers face additional compliance costs compared to competitors outside the EU. This could lead to market imbalances and unfair competition, potentially shifting steel production to regions with less stringent environmental regulations, thereby outsourcing emissions rather than reducing them globally.
- **Potential for Greenwashing and Certification Integrity:** While the framework aims to fight greenwashing, there may be concerns about the integrity of the certification process. Ethical challenges arise if companies manipulate or misrepresent their carbon removal efforts to meet certification standards without genuinely reducing their environmental impact.
- **Community Engagement and Inclusivity:** In the process of transitioning to sustainable steel production, it is crucial to involve affected communities in decision-making. Ethical considerations arise if there is a lack of transparent and inclusive engagement with communities impacted by changes in the steel industry.

Social Implication:

- **Economic Disruptions and Job Losses:** The transition away from traditional, carbon-intensive methods such as the blast furnace process may lead to economic disruptions within the steel industry. Job losses, particularly in regions heavily reliant on these methods, could result in social and economic hardships for workers and their communities.
- **Global Carbon Emissions:** The focus on certifying carbon removals within the EU might not directly address the global nature of climate change. Steel, being a globally traded commodity, raises questions about the EU's responsibility for emissions throughout the entire supply chain. The framework inadequately considers the broader social responsibility in a global context.
- **Social Equity in Transition Benefits:** The benefits of transitioning to more sustainable steel production methods need to be distributed equitably. If certain segments of the industry or specific regions disproportionately bear the costs of compliance while others enjoy the benefits, it raises questions about fairness and social equity.
- **Inclusive Decision-Making and Stakeholder Engagement:** Social considerations extend to the inclusivity of decision-making processes. Ensuring that stakeholders, including workers, communities, and smaller businesses, have a voice in shaping and implementing the transition is crucial for socially responsible governance.

6 Recommendations

Increasing usage of Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) Process: Increasing usage of Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) Process: Steel is manufactured throughout the European Union (EU), mostly through the 'primary' Blast Furnace - Basic Oxygen Furnace (BF-BOF) steelmaking route and the 'secondary' Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) route. We can make EAF our primary steelmaking route by increasing its usage in steel industries.

Implementing the Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) process in the European Union's steel industry requires a strategic and systematic approach to maximize carbon emission reduction and enhance sustainability. Key measures include improving scrap steel collection and recycling. The EU should focus on increasing the availability of high-quality scrap by establishing efficient recycling infrastructure, collaborating with steel-waste-generating industries, and promoting responsible disposal practices. Investments in upgrading and expanding EAF facilities, coupled with the construction of new ones, can boost the capacity for utilizing recycled scrap. Modernizing EAF technology, through advanced electrode and furnace lining materials and digital technologies, enhances energy efficiency and productivity while further reducing emissions. Supporting research and development initiatives for innovative steelmaking technologies, including exploring low-carbon energy sources like renewables for EAFs, accelerates the transition to cleaner practices. Collaborative efforts between industry, research institutions, and government bodies, along with policy measures and regulatory frameworks incentivizing low-carbon steel production, provide impetus. Implementing carbon pricing mechanisms and emissions trading systems creates economic incentives for prioritizing sustainability in the steel industry.

Utilization of Green Hydrogen: The iron and steel sector can achieve carbon neutrality by utilizing green hydrogen in the EAF process and direct reduction of iron ore. It represents a transformative approach in the steel industry. With HDRI-EAF technology, specific emissions from EU steel production could be reduced by over 35% (Bhaskar et al., 2020). Green hydrogen, produced through renewable energy sources, serves as a clean alternative to traditional hydrogen derived from fossil fuels. In this innovative process, hydrogen acts as a reducing agent in the direct reduction of iron ore, facilitating the conversion of iron oxides into metallic iron. The EAF process, known for its energy efficiency and flexibility, complements this green hydrogen-based direct reduction by melting the iron and alloying it with other elements to produce high-quality steel. This integrated approach not only reduces carbon emissions by eliminating the reliance on carbon-intensive coke in the traditional blast furnace but also contributes to the overall decarbonization of the steel production chain. The synergy between green hydrogen and the EAF process underscores a sustainable pathway for the steel industry, aligning with global efforts to combat climate change and transition towards a low-carbon future. This innovation highlights the industry's commitment to environmental responsibility, offering a model for achieving carbon-neutral steel production while fostering resilience and competitiveness in a rapidly evolving market.

Applying CCUS Technology: Steel industries can also employ CCUS technologies to capture CO₂ emitted in iron and steel production. The distinctive feature is the permanent underground storage of CO₂ through CCS. This process contributes to reducing carbon emissions and mitigating the environmental impact of steel manufacturing by securely storing captured carbon dioxide beneath the Earth's surface.

The expansion of CO₂ transportation infrastructure and the advancement of CO₂ capture technology will be made possible by CCUS growth. A shared CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure that numerous businesses can use could be an effective and affordable solution to meet climate targets, given many steel mills are situated in industrial clusters near other emitters (*Carbon-Capture-Use-and-Storage-2023.Pdf*, n.d.). The adoption of Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) technology in the European Union's steel industry is gaining prominence, especially in light of the proposed carbon removal certification framework. Implementing CCUS to reduce carbon emissions requires a meticulous evaluation of technological, economic, and legal aspects. Prior to implementation, a comprehensive assessment of steel manufacturing facilities, considering emission scopes, process intricacies, and economic feasibility, is imperative.

The selection of post-combustion, pre-combustion, or oxy-fuel combustion for Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) in steel production depends on specific procedures, from iron ore reduction to final product manufacturing. Robust infrastructure, including pipelines for transporting captured CO₂, is crucial for effective carbon capture, transportation, and storage. Engagement with regulatory authorities ensures compliance with emission reduction policies and standards, facilitating access to support and incentives. Financial incentives, subsidies, or tax credits from the EU or member states support the initial investment for CCUS adoption. Continuous monitoring, process adjustments, and public communication are essential for accurate reporting and garnering support for CCUS programs.

Top Gas Recycling' (TGR) Technology: Critical innovative technologies—like Top Gas Recycling—are important in raising energy efficiency and lowering CO₂ emissions in the steel industry. Top Gas Recycling (TGR) technology offers a viable solution for reducing carbon emissions in the steel industry within the European Union (EU). This innovative approach addresses the release of carbon monoxide (CO) and other gases during the steelmaking process. Traditional steel production emits carbon monoxide as a byproduct, contributing to environmental pollution. Top Gas Recycling (TGR) technology addresses this issue by capturing and recycling released gases, especially carbon monoxide, within the steel plant. Instead of releasing these gases into the atmosphere, TGR repurposes them. The captured carbon monoxide serves a dual role, acting as a reducing agent in steelmaking for enhanced operational efficiency and serving as a valuable internal fuel source, reducing reliance on external energy. TGR significantly lowers the carbon footprint of steel manufacturing, aligning with the EU's emission reduction targets and sustainability goals. Emphasizing circular economy principles, TGR minimizes waste, optimizes resource use, and provides operational cost savings. Efficient use of recycled gases decreases dependence on external energy sources, enhancing overall cost-effectiveness. TGR adoption underscores a commitment to innovation, making steel producers in the EU leaders in responsible and sustainable production, meeting the growing demand for environmentally conscious practices.

7 Conclusion

The steel industry's contribution to carbon emissions in the EU has prompted the need for innovative solutions to align with the EU's climate goals. The Carbon Removal Certification Framework may introduce additional pressures on the industry to reduce emissions, leading to a focus on cleaner technologies and processes. The framework also offers incentives for innovation, potentially driving the adoption of new technologies, such as Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) and the use of green hydrogen in the Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) process.

The implications on the steel industry extend beyond environmental considerations, influencing market competitiveness, supply chain dynamics, financial implications, and legal obligations. While the certification process may incur additional costs for the industry, it also opens avenues for green financing and enhances market reputation among environmentally conscious consumers. In light of these implications, the study recommends specific measures for the steel industry to align with the Carbon Removal Certification Framework. The increased utilization of the Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) process, incorporating green hydrogen, and implementing CCUS technology are proposed strategies to reduce carbon emissions and achieve certification. These strategies not only align with the framework's objectives but also position the steel industry as a leader in sustainable practices.

Furthermore, the adoption of 'Top Gas Recycling' (TGR) technology is highlighted as a critical innovation for improving energy efficiency and reducing CO₂ emissions in the steel industry. This technology, along with other proposed measures, underscores the industry's commitment to environmental responsibility and resilience in a rapidly evolving market.

In summary, embracing innovative technologies and sustainable practices will not only ensure compliance with certification requirements but also contribute to the broader goals of carbon neutrality and environmental sustainability set by the European Union. The steel industry's proactive engagement with the framework can serve as a model for other sectors seeking to balance industrial progress with environmental responsibility.

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